

CERTIFICATE OF PUBLICATION

YEAR: 2024

AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL

ISSN: 3048-7951

A QUARTERLY MULTIDISCIPLINARY BLIND PEER REVIEWED
& REFEREED ONLINE INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

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Editor-in-Chief
AD EDUXIAN JOURNAL
(ISSN: 3048-7951)
Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh, India

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